

Work-Life Balance Among Private Hospital Nurses – A Study In Mysuru City

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Abstract

Working in the health care sector is distinctive compared to other industries. Nurses working in hospitals play a vital role to maintain the health-status of patients. Nursing is the protection, promotion and optimization of health centers. In nursing, the health requirement of others is paramount instead of their own, in this case, a woman may find trouble in managing work-life balance. The health workers come across multiple challenges like heavy workloads, overtime, irregular shifts, physical and psychological stress which increases the risk of burnouts and depression. The current paper focuses on work-life balance dilemmas faced by nurses working in private hospitals and suggestions to the hospital management to implement effective and feasible working conditions to overcome the issues. They must introduce work-life balance policies to provide formal support at the workplace and optimize nursing for the wellbeing of nurses, their family and also patients. This paper figures out data from nurses that they don't have enough time to spend with their family and various other reasons which finally create stress and issue of work-life balance.

Keywords: Work-life balance, nurses, stress, family and health.

Introduction

Each employee has to maintain a balance between personal and professional life. In order to have a successful life, people are ready to provide more time to fulfill the objectives of life. To achieve the goals in professional life, people may have to compromise with their personal life and occasionally results in affecting mental peace. The health care industry is facing stiff competition and challenges to provide better treatment facilities at economical prices. The role of Nurses is paramount in determining the effectiveness and efficiency of the treatment provided to the patients. Internationally, there is a serious shortage of nurses. One reason for this shortage is due to the work environment in which nurses practice. In a recent review of the empirical human factors and ergonomic literature specific to nursing performance, nurses were found to work in generally poor environmental conditions. Some countries and states have passed legislation regarding acceptable nurse-to-patient ratios. The fast-paced and unpredictable nature of health care places nurses at risk for injuries and illnesses, including high occupational stress. Nursing is a particularly stressful profession, and nurses consistently identify stress as a major work-related concern and have among the highest levels of occupational stress when compared to other professions. This stress is caused by the environment, psychosocial stressors, and the demands of nursing, including new technology that must be mastered, the emotional labor involved in nursing, physical labor, shift work, and high workload. This stress puts nurses at risk for short-term and long-term health problems, including sleep disorders, depression, mortality, psychiatric disorders, stress-related illnesses, and illness in general. Nurses are at risk of developing compassion fatigue and moral distress, which can worsen mental health. They also have very high rates of occupational burnout and emotional exhaustion. Burnout and exhaustion increase the risk for illness, medical error, and suboptimal care provision. Nurses are also at risk for violence and abuse in the workplace. Violence is typically perpetrated by non-staff (e.g. patients or family), whereas abuse is typically perpetrated by other hospital personnel. An official study reveals that the healthcare market can increase three-fold to Rs 8.6 trillion (US\$ 133.44 billion) by 2022. There are several interventions that can mitigate the occupational hazards of nursing. They can be individual-focused or organization-focused. Individual-focused interventions include stress management programs, which can be customized to individuals. Stress management programs can reduce anxiety, sleep disorders, and other symptoms of stress. Organizational interventions focus on reducing stressful aspects of the work environment by defining stressful characteristics and developing solutions to them. Using organizational and individual interventions together is most effective at reducing stress on nurses.

Review of literature

Every research backed by researches conducted earlier. The following are the studies have taken into consideration for the best outcomes.

1. Goyal. B(2014) in his study on the work-life balance of nurse and lady doctors discussed the importance of the work-life balance of nurses in private hospitals, as there is high work pressure in private hospitals which impacts the negative effect on the women to maintain a healthy family life. The study revealed that 67% of lady doctors and nurses found difficult to manage their household and office work, they cannot give the required time for their kids and also concluded that 81% of nurses prefer for flexible work arrangement which should be provided by the organization to maintain a healthy work-life balance.
2. Marie and Umesh Maiya(2015) in their observation found that the work-life balance of women is most affected when it comes to health care sectors, it may be because of shift work, overtime, night work, long working hours which put a lot of stress on nurse professionally and personally. In their analysis, they interpreted that 55% of women workers at health care center have less time to spend quality time with family members, 30% of nurses say that they often have to work for overtime and long working hours which create stress an health issues like frequent headaches and acidity problems. Further 57% of nurses strongly disagree that family support does not matter in their work-life balance aspect. Dr. Ipseeta satpathy, Dr. B Chandra Mohan Patnaik, Sasmitha Jena (2014) in a comparative study of work-life balance on nursing staff working in private and government hospitals to analyze the general perception towards the personal and professional life with the help of Demographic factors which results that there is no much difference in work stress between government and private staff rather they observed that the WLB of the nurses is most affected in case of married women as compares to un-married staffs. They say that management must look after some aspects like work timing, monetary benefits, support team, creating a tension-free working culture and other social aspects like maternity and paternity benefits, stress-relieving workshops and recognition and reward for better performance, etc to improve the efficiency of work among woman nurse.
3. Lakshmi, K.S., Ramachandran, T. & Boohene, D.(2012) they used tools like multiple regression and T-test to find out that how for satisfactory and stress factors are influencing work-life balance variable, in their comparative study on nurses in government and private hospital, where government workers have various benefits like
4. The Journal was given by Eshwari and Saravanan. S (2011) where they randomly selected nurses from hospitals of Coimbatore city states that the organization should recognize the frustration of women nurses like lack of internal empowerment, burnouts, turnover and elimination of external sources will decrease the efficiency and satisfaction of nurse but the study is silent about the effect of stress on patient safety, quality care and patient outcomes.
5. H Imai, H Nakao, M Tsuching, Y Kuroda and T Katah in their article titled “Burnout and work environment of public health nurses involved in mental health care” – involves a comparison of Burnouts among community psychiatric nurses with public health nurses. Burnout is a state of emotional, physical and mental exhaustion caused by excessive and prolonged stress. It reduces the connectivity between different parts of the brain which reduces the creativity and skill of a person.

6. The study conducted by Beh, L. S., & Loo, L. H. (2012) gave a detailed description of the meaning of stress, the main source of job stress and the mechanism of coping with job stress. According to their observation, the main source of job stress is the workload and other related factors are working conditions, conflicts among peers, inconsiderate superior, the system of work, etc. many times the high expectations which are beyond their abilities also lead to job stress. This job stress results in psychological and physical disorders among them. The suggestion provided to balance the work is a control mechanism and social support mechanism.
7. 'Nurses strategies for coping with job stress'-a journal by Al-Aameri.& Al-Fawzan (1998) found various job stressors in which the main stressor are organizational structure and climate, and the job itself. According to his study, homework is not the reason for work stress but there is an exception in this case regarding age and marital status. The writer opined that some job stressors can be managed positively and others can be eliminated with the help of managers and management policies.
8. Gururaja, U., Maiya, E.S., & Devi, A. G. (2013) in their journal "Perceptions and Attitude towards Quality of Work-life Balance among nursing teachers" state the different opinion that the work-life balance and job satisfaction are positively correlated as per their observation. The survey also says that employee needs flexible working hours to complete their task and frame their work. They conclude that work-life balance and job satisfaction go hand in hand which leads to a satisfying career for the employee.
9. Keeton K, Fenner DE, Johnson TRB, Hayward RA (2007) in the journal "Predictors of physician career satisfaction, work-life balance, and burnout" the article says that both men and women are highly satisfied with their jobs and are happy towards work-life balance as they are most focused on their career.

Research gap

The above papers lack information about earning satisfaction, leave the facility, job security, leave encashment, and other perquisites which increases the efficiency of an employee. The nurse working at private hospitals has fewer benefits as compared to public hospitals. The present study highlights the work-life balance of nurses working in private hospitals.

Scope and limitation of the study

- The study highlights physical stress on nurses due to the type of work allotted to them.
- The study relates to job satisfaction and work policies with the work-life balance of nurses.
- The study was restricted to an only nurse working at private hospitals.
- The study limits its geographical area up to Mysore only.

Research methodology

- The respondents are chosen from a private hospital in Mysore city.
- The respondents are selected on a simple random sampling method.
- Structured questionnaires are given to collect data and they were interviewed.
- The sample size was restricted to 110.
- Microsoft Excel is used for the analysis.
- The bar graph and pie charts have been used to interpret the data

Analysis and interpretation

Age-wise distribution of respondents

Age Group	Percentage
Less than 25 years	25
25-35	13
35-45	46
Above 45 years	17

Graph no. 1

The above pie chart shows that there are 25% of the nurses who are less than 25 years, 13% of them are between 25 to 35 years, 45% of them are falling under the age limits of 35-45 years and 17 % of them are in the bracket of 45 years and above.

Table no.2

Experience wise distribution of respondents	
Years	Percentage
1-5 years	29
10-15 years	41
15-20 years	10
20 and above	20

Graph no. 2

The above table shows the experience distribution of nurses, 29 % of the nurses have 1 to 5 years of experience, 41% of them have 10-15 years of experience 10% of them have 15 to 20 years of experience and at last 20 % of them have more than 20 years of experience.

No. Of children	
Nos	Percentage
0	10
1	75
2	10
3	5

The table shows that the number of children they have, 10% of them have no children. 75% of them have only one child, 10% of them have 2 children and merely 5% of them have 3 children.

Marital status	
Status	Percentage
Unmarried	10
Married	85
Divorcee	3
Widow	3

The table shows the marital status of the nurses. 10% of them are unmarried. 85% of them are married, 3% of them are divorcee and 3% of them are a widow.

No. Of dependents	
No.s	Percentage
0	10
1	8
2	38
3	38
More than 3	6

The table shows that the number of dependents they have 10% of them have no children. 8% of them have a single dependent, 38% of them have 2 dependents, merely 38% of them have 3 dependents and more than 6% of them have more than 3 dependents.

Salary per month	
Particulars	Percentage
less than 10000	29
10000-15000	46
15000-20000	12
20000and above	13

The above table shows the distribution of the salary of nurses per month. 29% of them are drawing less than 10000 salaries per month. 46% of them are between 10000 to 15000, 12% of them have salaries between 15000 to 20000 and 13% of them have more than 20000 salaries per month.

Type of family	
Status	Percentage
Nuclear	97
HUF	3

The above table shows the type of family of the nurses. Only 3% of them are living in the Hindu undivided family and the rest 97% is from a nuclear family. This shows the drastic reduction in HUF in India.

Spending quality time with family				
Particulars	Spouse	Children	Parents	In-laws
Highly satisfied	2	4	8	22
Satisfied	8	8	21	17
Neutral	13	5	7	30
Unsatisfied	50	67	52	17
Highly unsatisfied	28	16	13	15

The above table shows the level of satisfaction with the quality time spent by the nurses with their families. The satisfaction towards quality time spent with a spouse is as follows. Only 2% of them are highly satisfied, 8% of them are satisfied 13% or neither satisfied not dissatisfied, 50% of them are unsatisfied and 28% of them are highly dissatisfied. The satisfaction towards quality time spent with their children are as follows. Only 4% of them are highly satisfied, 8% of them are satisfied 5% or neither satisfied not dissatisfied, 67% of them are unsatisfied and 16% of them are highly dissatisfied. The satisfaction towards quality time spent to meet their parents is as follows. Only 8% of them are highly satisfied, 21% of them are satisfied 7% or neither satisfied not dissatisfied, 52% of them are unsatisfied and 13% of them are highly dissatisfied. The satisfaction towards quality time spent in-laws is as follows. Only 22% of them are highly satisfied, 17% of them are satisfied 30% or neither satisfied not dissatisfied, 17% of them are unsatisfied and 15% of them are highly dissatisfied

Spending quality time for self and social interaction				
Particulars	Self	Family Functions	Meeting friends	Interaction on social media
Highly satisfied	8	3	4	2
Satisfied	17	10	25	3
Neutral	7	14	11	8
Unsatisfied	56	41	48	51
Highly unsatisfied	13	32	12	37

The above table shows the level of satisfaction with the quality time spent by the nurses with their-self and social interaction. The satisfaction towards quality time spent on themselves is as follows. Only 8% of them are highly satisfied, 17% of them are satisfied 7% or neither are satisfied not dissatisfied, 56% of them are unsatisfied and 13% of them are highly dissatisfied. The satisfaction towards quality time spent on their family functions are as follows. Only 3% of them are highly satisfied, 10% of them are satisfied 14% or neither are satisfied not dissatisfied, 41% of them are unsatisfied and 32% of them are highly dissatisfied. The satisfaction towards quality time spent to meet their friends are as follows. Only 4% of them are highly satisfied, 25% of them are satisfied 11% or neither satisfied not dissatisfied, 48% of them are unsatisfied and 12% of them are highly dissatisfied. The satisfaction towards quality time spent active in social media is as follows. Only 2% of them are highly satisfied, 3% of them are satisfied 8% or neither are satisfied not dissatisfied, 51% of them are unsatisfied and 37% of them are highly dissatisfied.

Difficulty with work timings					
Particulars	Number hours spent on duty	Additional shifts	Shift timings	Traveling time to workplace	Inflexibility in working time
Always	32	22	20	33	33
Sometimes	45	46	18	29	29
Neutral	7	12	21	20	20
Rarely	10	8	17	13	13
Very rarely	7	13	25	4	4

The above table shows the level of difficulty faced by the nurses to cope with the work timings is as follows. The level difficulty faced by the number of hours to spending on the duty is as follows. 32% of them are always facing difficulty, 45% of them are feel difficult sometimes 7% are neutral about, 10% of them are rarely feeling it's

difficult and 7% of them are rarely feeling it's difficult. The level difficulty faced by going with an additional shift is as follows. 22% of them are always facing difficulty, 46% of them are feel difficult sometimes 12% are neutral about the number hours spending on the duty, 8% of them are rarely feel it's difficult and 13% of them are rarely feeling it's difficult. The level difficulty faced by traveling time from home to the workplace is as follows. 33% of them are always facing the difficulty, 29% of them are feel difficult sometimes 20% are neutral about the number hours spending on the duty, 13% of them are rarely feels it's difficult and 4% of them are rarely feeling it's difficult. The level difficulty faced by inflexible work is as follows. 33% of them are always facing the difficulty, 29% of them are feel difficult sometimes 20% are neutral about the number hours spending on the duty, 13% of them are rarely feels it's difficult and 4% of them are rarely feeling it's difficult.

Frequent physical health issues				
Particulars	Headache	Whole-body pain	Fatigue	Backache
Always	33	38	22	47
Sometimes	38	47	46	38
Neutral	18	3	12	10
Rarely	9	8	8	5
Very rarely	3	5	13	1

The above table shows frequent physical health issues faced by the nurses to cope with the work as well as family is as follows. The frequency of the headache faced by them is as follows. 33% of them are always troubled by the headache, 38% of them are sometimes, 18% are neutral, 10% are rarely and 7% of them are very rarely troubled by the headache. The frequency of whole-body pain for the nurses is as follows. 38% of them are always troubled, 47% of them are sometimes troubled by 3% are neutral about the trouble of, 8% them are rarely and 5% of them are very rarely troubled by whole-body pain. The frequency of fatigue for the nurses is as follows. 47% of them are always troubled, 38% of them are sometimes 10% are neutral about, 5% of them are rarely and 1% of them are very rarely troubled by fatigue. The frequency of back-ache for the nurses is as follows. 47% of them are always troubled, 38% of them are sometimes 10% are neutral, 5% of them are rarely and 1% of them are very rarely troubled by back-ache.

Work environment and policy				
Particulars	Leaves	Peer group relationships	Remuneration and Appraisals	Management coordination
Highly satisfied	25	32	28	42
Satisfied	45	53	39	37
Neutral	11	4	10	10
Unsatisfied	17	5	9	5
Highly unsatisfied	3	6	13	7

The above table shows the level of satisfaction with the work environment and policy. The satisfaction towards leaves is as follows. Only 25% of them are highly satisfied, 45% of them are satisfied 11% or neither satisfied not dissatisfied, 17% of them are unsatisfied and 3% of them are highly dissatisfied. The satisfaction towards peer group relationship is as follows. Only 32% of them are highly satisfied, 53% of them are satisfied 4% or neither are satisfied not dissatisfied, 5% of them are unsatisfied and 6% of them are highly dissatisfied. The satisfaction towards remunerations and appraisals are as follows. 28% of them are highly satisfied, 39% of them are satisfied 10% or neither are satisfied not dissatisfied, 9% of them are unsatisfied and 13% of them are highly dissatisfied. The satisfaction towards management coordination is as follows. Only 42% of them are highly satisfied, 37% of them are satisfied 10% or neither satisfied not dissatisfied, 5% of them are unsatisfied and 7% of them are highly dissatisfied

Psychological health issues						
Particulars	Sleeping disorder	Always thinking about job or family	Depression	Aggressiveness	Lack of concentration	Anxiety
Always	42	33	22	29	0	28
Sometimes	37	38	46	38	18	33
Neutral	10	18	12	17	57	20
Rarely	5	9	8	10	17	10
Very rarely	7	3	13	7	9	8

The above table shows the psychological health issues faced by the nurses to cope with the work as well as family is as follows. The frequency of the sleeping disorder faced by them is as follows. 42% of them are always troubled by a sleeping disorder, 37% of them are sometimes, 10% are neutral, 5% are rarely and 7% of them are very rarely troubled by the sleeping disorder. The frequency of thinking about a job or family by the nurses is as follows. 33% of them are always, 38% of them are sometimes by 18% are neutral, 9% of them are rare and 3% of them very rarely think about job or family. The frequency of depression faced by the nurses is as follows. 22% of them are always, 46% of them are sometimes 12% are neutral about, 8% of them are rarely and 13% of them are very rarely faced depression. The frequency of lack of concentration felt by nurses is as follows. 0% of them are always, 18% of them are sometimes 57% are neutral, 17% of them are rarely and 9% of them are very rarely had a lack of concentration. The frequency of anxiety felt by nurses is as follows. 28% of them are always, 33% of them are sometimes 20% are neutral, 10% of them are rarely and 8% of them are very rarely felt anxiety.

Findings and suggestions

All the researches aimed at finding the problems faced by society and try to provide solutions in a better manner by understanding the problem in different dimensions. The following are the research findings.

- The above study indicates the difficulty with work timing and health issues both physically and psychologically among nurses at their workplace.
- The nurse working at private hospitals have over workload which affects their work-life balance.
- Though the work at private hospitals has scope for good working conditions and better work policies but the job satisfaction and job security compared to government hospitals are very less.

- The work procedure and working conditions in the health industry are different as compared to other sectors.

Suggestions

In the light of research findings, the following Suggestions are most appropriate to adopt by private hospitals.

- Proper working conditions and systematic work policies need to be created by the hospital management to maintain work balance.
- Workload and working shifts should be flexible to nurse so that they can spend reasonable time with their family.
- The management should take initiative to include various benefits to the nurses to increase their working efficiency and job satisfaction.

Conclusion

At present women forms an integral part of the Indian workforce, that too when the matter is about health care, after doctors the next person who contributes to the life of the patients are nurses. As women are blessed with emotions and special features like caring, this motivates them to select this profession. From the above observation, we can say that, though the national policy for the empowerment of women provides a framework for plans and programs aimed at women's advancement in different fields but the hospitals that too private hospitals lag in providing job satisfaction among its employees. The job of nurse lacks job improvements, performance appraisals, job satisfaction and job achievement. The main reason for job stress are heavy workloads, long working hours, burnouts, etc. women need to balance her shoulders with professional goals and family requirements. The physical and psychological stress due to the work environment may put an adverse effect on the work-life balance of nurses. These nurses should get individual attention as well as organizational attention to overcome their barriers.

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